

Axial ligands as interplanar spacers in macrocyclic solids

Nadir Ana Wiederkehr

Departamento de Física, C.C.N.E., Universidade Federal de Santa Maria, 97119-900 Santa Maria R.S., Brazil

E-mail : Anaw67@aol.com

Manuscript received 5 January 1999, accepted 5 May 1999

2,9,16,23-Tetra(neopentoxo)phthalocyaninato of cobalt ligand coordinated compounds of cyanide, pyridine, 4-cyanopyridine, pyrazine and 4,4'-bipyridyl, are isolated as solid powders and correlated to Langmuir-Blodgett film structure and compared to thermally induced film-surface ligand coordination processes.

Variations of the phthalocyanine molecular structure by introduction of spacers, induces molecular reactivity in specially designed and preprogrammed basic modules reticulated by conjugated bonds. The axial coordination of basic ligands has proven to enhance the degree of the molecular organization and to improve experimental reproductibility. The ability of metal phthalocyanines to coordinate to nitrogenous ligand-bridges is well known¹ and correlation with peripheral substituents extensively investigated².

[2,9,16,24-Tetra(neopentoxo)phthalocyaninato]cobalt (CoTnPc), CoTnPc.L (L = ligand; L = cyanide, pyridine and 4-cyanopyridine) (1 : 1), and axial binuclear units. (CoTnPc)₂.L (L = bidentate ligand; L = pyrazine, 4,4'-bipyridyl) (2 : 1) were isolated as solid powders, characterized as Langmuir-Blodgett films and related to thermally induced surface ligand coordination processes. The film structure of CoTnPc and the monoadducts CoTnPc.PY or 4-CN-PY can be related to the interaction between neighboring rings and neopentoxo substituents. The construction of dimeric (CoTnPc)₂.PYZ or 4,4'-bipy or stacked metallophthalocyanines (L = CN) with bisaxially bridged ligands allows electron delocalization by π - π overlap³ enhancing orderliness and fluidity of the formed films. The result is a stack of molecules with the axis in the film plane and the macrocycles with some angle to the surface ('edge-on' configuration).

Results and Discussion

CoTnPc coordinated complexes (CoTnPc/L) (Table 1) were prepared according to conventional methods¹⁻³, and characterized by elemental analysis, ¹H NMR, IR and electronic spectra. The molecular structures for non-bridging and bridging ligands are presented in Fig. 1.

Elemental analysis shows different stoichiometry for CoTnPc/L compounds. When L (ligand) = CN, PY, 4-CN-

PY the proportion is 1(CoTnPc) : 1(L), while for bidentate ligands (L = PYZ, 4,4'-bipy) the relation is clearly 2CoTnPc : 1(L), characterized as axial binuclear phthalocyanine compounds.

Fig. 1. Structures of tetra(neopentoxo)phthalocyaninatocobalt/L compounds.

The cobalt unpaired electrons are at d_{z^2} orbital with some d_{xz} and d_{yz} orbital contribution, which decreases when L-strength increases^{1a,b,c}. The addition of one more L for CoTnPc/L non-bridging ligands (L = PY, 4-CN-PY) could cause out-of-plane Co displacement; symmetrical and non-symmetrical interactions are proposed in Fig. 1.

By inspection of Table 1, CoTnPc/CN presents the inclusion of 5H₂O molecules; according to literature^{6b,8} cyanide can establish hydrogen bonds to water molecules (of crystallization) with formation of CoTnPc.CN.5H₂O. Solubility properties and slight wavelength ($\lambda_{\max} = Q$ -band) shifts were detected solely for CoTnPc.CN.5H₂O in donating solvents; in low D.N. (donor numbers) solvents, strengthening of conditions leads to de-metallation. The unshifted UV-vis spectra for CoTnPc/L (L = aromatic ligands) can be related to excitation coupling between excitation transitions of the Pc(phthalocyanine) rings^{9a}.

IR spectra for CoTnPc and CoTnPc/L were determined in KBr pellets. Structural information concerning central metal and adduct formation (Table 1) from band shift or band intensity can be related to molecular symmetry^{1,2,5}. Table 1 presents shifts and intensities of the stretching bands assigned for CoTnPc (square-planar) and CoTnPc/L (pyramidal).

Table 1. IR spectral data (cm⁻¹) of compounds*

Compd	$\nu(\text{CN})$	$\nu(\text{Co-N})_{\text{ring}}(\text{Pc})$	$\nu(\text{C-N})_{\text{outersphere}}(\text{Pc})$
CoTnPc		804 m	1380 vs
CoTnPc.CN	2123	824 w	1385 vw
CoTnPc.PY.5H ₂ O		822 w	1385 w
(CoTnPc) ₂ .PYZ		823 w	1385 m
(CoTnPc) ₂ .4,4'-bipy		823 w	1385 s

s = strong, m = medium, w = weak, v = very

*All compounds gave satisfactory C, H and N analyses.

The appearance of the 2123 cm⁻¹ band for CoTnPc.CN.5H₂O indicates Co^{III}-bound terminal cyano groups ($\nu_{\text{free ion}} 2080 \text{ cm}^{-1}$); the shift to higher wavenumbers indicates that mostly σ -donation is involved and π -backbonding plays a minor role^{1,6}. The increase of the bond length of Co-CN, which is the result of donor-acceptor interaction has shown in IR peak with low absorbance values, characteristic of symmetry losses.

The band located at 804 cm⁻¹ for CoTnPc is characterized as being cobalt-nitrogen (Pc-from the phthalocyanine ring) vibration^{5,6}. The shift to higher wavelengths ($\sim 823 \text{ cm}^{-1}$) for CoTnPc/L (L = CN, PY, PYZ, 4,4'-bipy and 4-CN-PY), confirms cofacial ligand coordination with same geometry for all ligands under investigation. The Pc macrocycle symmetry changes ($D_{4h} \rightarrow C_{4v}$) due to axial ligation is insensitive to ligand nature and/or bond length variations of Co-N (PC). Absorptions sensitive to coordinated ligands (L) and/or metal are in the 100–500 cm⁻¹ region^{1a,2b}; the unpaired electron located in a d_{z^2} orbital is

difficult to monitor by usual spectroscopic techniques, once the ground state configuration remains unchanged^{1b}.

IR band located at 1380 cm⁻¹, shows difference in intensity for CoTnPc (square-planar) and CoTnPc/L (square-pyramidal) attributed to C-N outer-sphere Pc vibrations^{1a,b,2a,5}. The accumulation of electron density on the outer carbons and nitrogen atoms^{1a,b,2a} can be related to electron back-donation from the metal d_{π} orbitals to the ligand π^* (e_g) antibonding wavefunction. The intensity order is shown in Table 1 and explained as a function of π -acceptor and σ -donor strength of the axial ligands and electronic population of Pc molecular orbitals. As the metal charge increases from Co^{II} to Co^{III}, the band reduces intensity and even disappears, in the case of CN⁻. The CN coordination to Co-Pc lowers the energy of the metal d -orbitals and decreases the interaction with the 1 $e_g(\pi^*)$ orbital decreasing the difference between average values of 'internal' and 'external' C-N bond lengths of the Pc macrocycle. The following sequence indicates increase of electron charge, energy of d -orbitals on the metal and interaction with the 1 $e_g(\pi^*)$ orbital of the phthalocyanine (Pc); the angular momentum consequently increases in the opposite sense :

Increase of electron density on C-N (Pc) bonds	CoTnPc.CN.5H ₂ O CoTnPc PY (CoTnPc) ₂ PYZ (CoTnPc) ₂ .4,4'-bipy	↑	Increase of the angular momentum
	↓ CoTnPc		

¹H NMR measurements for Co^{III}TnPc/L (L = CN and PY) diamagnetic compounds in DMSO-*d*₆, have shown decreased paramagnetism for central Co. The indication of complex formation with high field shift due to Pc-ring current shifted proton signals of the axial coordinated pyridine (PY) with respect to the non-coordinated ligands, evidencing dependence of the ground-state electron density.

Monolayer formation and Langmuir-Blodgett techniques :

Film structure, degree of order and experimental reproductibility of phthalocyanine compounds is dependent on the central metal and attachment of substituents which confer distinct tendencies for aggregation. Nevertheless, there is the risk of a multilayer ('slipped stack' configuration) formation for Pc compounds¹¹, the effect may present smaller area per molecule (APM) than those expected by considering molecular dimensions⁹, the limiting value is considered as compatible with the assumption of a true monolayer on the water subphase. Mononuclear phthalocyanine derivatives have been most extensively studied by Langmuir-Blodgett (LB) techniques^{9b,12}; dimers^{2,6,9} and oligomers^{1d,2a,3,6} appeared recently. The LB behavior of monomeric, dimeric and oligomeric CoTnPc and CoTnPc/L as bi-dimensional structures (Fig. 3) is related to the respective isolated powders (Fig. 1). CoTnPc and CoTnPc/L form LB films with short alkyl side-chains-pentoxy

groups ($R = C_5H_{11}$) but with reproducible compression/decompression properties. Fig. 2 presents the surface pressure versus area isotherms at 15° for monolayer CoTnPc and CoTnPc/L. The limiting areas per molecules (APM) are 160° and $105^\circ \text{ \AA}^2/\text{molecule}$ for CoTnPc and CoTnPc/L; the long molecular axis forms 40° and 60° , respectively, with the substrate (surface). The forces responsible for the angle shift are conformational in origin, imposed by electron delocalization through perpendicular orbitals provided by L. Even that ligands differ in length (PYZ = 680 pm ; $4,4'$ -bipy = 1110 pm)^{6b}, varying the inter-macrocycle distance, or L proportion (monoadducts, binuclear and macrocycles bridged via ligand compounds) did not alter APM for CoTnPc/L (L = CN, PY, 4-CN-PY, PYZ and $4,4'$ -bipy) due to method insensitivity.

ligands such as CN, PYZ and $4,4'$ -bipy, different structures are suggested : (i) monomeric (CoTnPc.CN.5H₂O) (3(b)), axial binuclear [(CoTnPc)₂.PYZ and $4,4'$ -bipy] units (3(c)) and macrocyclic bridged via ligand ('shish-kebab' polymers)³ structures (3(d)), which may be formed in different extends for CN and as second structural component for PYZ and $4,4'$ -bipy. The present work describes two distinct methods of preparation for CoTnPc/L compounds as : (i) isolated solids (LB deposition onto hydrophilic surfaces) (Table 1, Fig. 1) and (ii) surface ligand functionalization—thermally induced processes in aqueous medium. Reaction of CoTnPc \rightarrow CoTnPc/L (L = CN, PY, 4-CN-PY, PYZ, $4,4'$ -bipy) as direct surface derivatization : a preparative method for the coordination of basic ligands to macrocyclic structures, including phthalocyanine compounds. In the solid state the operative orbital interactions are the same as

Fig. 2. Surface pressure vs area per molecule isotherms for CoTnPc and CoTnPc/L (L = PYZ) on double-distilled water at 15° .

Langmuir-Blodgett (LB) deposition pattern showed distinct behavior : CoTnPc required hydrophobic surfaces—interaction between dichlorodimethylsilane and neopentoxy CH_3 groups (Z-type deposition), while CoTnPc/L hydrophilic surfaces—higher molecular polarity induces interaction through dipoles via OH groups of the substrate (Y-type deposition).

Fig. 3 presents a schematic representation for CoTnPc onto hydrophobic surfaces and CoTnPc/L on hydrophilic surfaces, for non-bridging ligands (L = PY, 4-CN-PY) and bridging ligands (L = CN, PYZ, $4,4'$ -bipy). For non-bridging ligands such as PY and 4-CN-PY, monoadducts are formed in the solid state (Fig. 1(a)); in analogy to the formed films (Fig. 3(b)), no axial driven (L) contacts between macrocyclic units are suggested; intermolecular distances are increased and crystal packing properties altered (packing loss). CoTnPc.PY and 4-CN-PY forms morphologically thicker film⁶ (high coverage) with apparent chemical inactivity to further surface reactions, if compared to the bisaxially mediated CoTnPc series. For bridging

those that govern molecular geometries and reactivity so that elements can be substituted, atoms intercalated, non-stoichiometries enhanced and electrons tuned^{14, 15}; the basic degrees of freedom are electronic and vibrational : cooperative Jahn-Teller transitions (electronic energy lowered by symmetry distortions)¹⁵. If phonons (vibrational instabilities) are responsible for structural changes, a displacive transition may result^{15, 16}. CoTnPc/L surface derivatized, presents electronic and vibrational modes strongly coupled in a concerted process of water inclusion and molecular rearrangement; crystallographically different from the parent CoTnPc/L compound, isolated as powder from non-aqueous medium. The static surface energy presents the following components: migration energy, binding energy, proximity energy (steric effect) and coupling (activation energy)¹⁶. Complexes of transition-metal present localized bonding with the highest occupied molecular orbitals either at the metal or at the ligand^{10, 11}. As a results, it is possible to change the charge distribution by changing the ligand(s) (changes on the energy of the Co *d*-orbital), with two

Fig. 3. Schematic drawing for the intermolecular contacts driven by ligand coordination processes of phthalocyanine films : (a) MPc; (b) MPc/L (L = non-bridging ligand, ex. : pyridine); (c) MPc/L (L = aromatic bidentate, ex. : pyrazine and 4,4'-bipyridyl); (d) MPc/L (L = bridging ligand, with σ -system, ex. : cyanide).

electronic states nearly degenerate, leading to vibronic interactions and environment sensitivity. An external perturbation (photons, electric field) can interconvert two nearly degenerate states as demonstrated for Fe^{II} spin-crossover (low- and high-spin state) complexes^{17a} in the LIESST (light-induced excited spin state trapping) effect. The spin conversion (due to temperature, pressure, coordination number and light exposure) of one molecule induces that of the neighboring molecules through electron-phonon coupling (coupling between the electronic states of the metal and the lattice phonon system through metal-ligand vibrations); abruptness and hysteresis are due to cooperativity in the solid state^{17b}. The existence of strong interactions between molecular units results in a pronounced cooperative effect characterized as discontinuous : strongly cooperative effects taking place in a narrow temperature range. Co^{II} d^7 compounds exhibit a $S = 3/2$ (HS : high - spin) \leftrightarrow $1/2$ (LS : low-spin) discontinuous spin conversion¹⁴ for CoTnPc systems under investigation. The weak field-HS and strong field-LS are two extreme possibilities; intermediate configurations are possible when the field is intermediate in

strength¹⁷. The originally Co^{II} TnPc compound is a high-spin complex ($S = 3/2$) and requires an activation energy to overcome the Franck-Condon barrier for the electron transfer and to form Co^{II} TnPc/L. The high-spin Co^{II} with three unpaired electrons [$\pi(d)^6$] [$\sigma^*(d)^1$] when transferring one electron to the π^* -orbital of L, acquires the low-spin d^6 configuration with no unpaired electrons.

For all ligands under investigation absorbance values are increased and λ_{max} shifted to higher wavelengths. Fig. 5 presents a set of time-dependent experiments for the CN surface coordination to CoTnPc, deposited by LB methods. The surface reaction achieves completeness (under the specified conditions) when 12 min time have elapsed. The processes can be classified as kinetic and thermodynamically controlled with the following variables : concentration and stirring of the CN solution (diffusion-controlled), temperature (most enthalpic), number of CoTnPc layers on the surface. In the LS state the e_g orbitals (antibonding character) are less populated than in the HS state. The HS \leftrightarrow LS crossover results in a shortening of the metal-ligand bond lengths. The strengthening of the metal-donor atom bond turns significant only when the low-spin (LS) configuration involves a filled t_{2g} subshell as in Co^{II} ²⁰. Additional changes of bond distances and angles of the ligand are dependent on the geometry of the ligand, the arrangement of the ligands around the metal and the crystal packing. Spin-state transitions are characterized by significant changes of distances and angles within the coordination around the involved metal; changes in geometry are concentrated in the central region of the molecules rather than in peripheral areas. The electronic rearrangement on the metal opposes outer molecular part rearrangement due to intermolecular crowding. These changes produce a simultaneous increase of the unit cell volume.

The spin transition associated with a crystallographic phase change is characterized as first order^{17c} when the electronic state of the molecules within the solid compound changes simultaneously with the crystallographic properties of the lattice.

The inclusion of linear π -electron-containing molecules increases considerably the system order¹⁰. The change from a lattice with a certain symmetry to another symmetry and the amplitude of the distortion is defined as order parameter¹⁴. If the long axis of the molecule is used as reference, θ the angle with the director axis (Z), the scalar long-range order parameter S is defined as¹⁵

$$S = 1/2 \langle 3 \cos^2\theta - 1 \rangle$$

The calculated value for CoTnPc is 0.25, and 0.70 for CoTnPc/L. The aggregation is considerably reduced for the latter compound, but remaining random related to the eight possible environments for tetra(neopentoxy) substituent groups¹³. The isomer mixture of tetra-substituted

Fig. 4. Normalized electronic absorption spectra of CoTnPc : (a) LB deposited onto hydrophobic glass slide, 28 layers, 7 cycles of Z-type transfer at 25 mN/m with subsequent dipping into aqueous solution of NaCN-3M at 90°, during 8 min; Q-band- λ_{\max} = 696 nm; B-band = 650 nm; absorbance/layer: 0.06. (b) Removal (by washings) with 2 ml of DMSO of (a)-surface; Q-band- λ_{\max} = 682 nm; abs. : 0.33 (1 cm quartz cell); B-band = 614 nm (Obs. : The spectrum is identical to CoTnPc.CN.5H₂O dissolved directly in DMSO). The upper inset is a normalized electronic spectra of CoTnPc: (a) LB deposited onto hydrophobic glass slide, 16 layers, 4 cycles of Z type transfer at 25 mN/m; Q-band- λ_{\max} = 686 nm; B-band = 640 nm; (b) Removal of (a) with 2 ml of DMSO; Q-band- λ_{\max} = 676 nm; abs.: 0.34; B-band = 612 nm.

phthalocyanines² leads to a lower degree of order in the solid state if compared to octa-substituted^{3,6}. In counterpart, tetra-substituted phthalocyanines possess a higher dipole moment caused by unsymmetrical arrangement of the substituents in the periphery, important for long distance energy transfer via dipole-dipole interactions. The insertion of ligands as interplanar spacers avoids aggregation, enhances compression/decompression properties by controlling intermolecular distances and molecular orientation.

The wavelength shift and absorbance ratio changes for CoTnPc and CoTnPc/L can be related to the electric vector of the light vibrating perpendicular to the surface presenting absorbance values due to perpendicular electric vector of light, A_{\perp} or parallel, A_{\parallel} ; the proportion $Abs_{\perp}/Abs_{\parallel} = D_{\beta}$ (dichroic ratio). The Pc transition dipole plane has a normal which is z' , θ is the formed angle between z' and the Z axes, sensitive to the Pc positional angle in relation to the dipping direction. By increase of the Pc angle, the polarization of the electric vector vibrating perpendicular to the surface is increased (maximum when $\theta = 90^{\circ}$). Experimental determination of the dichroic ratio for CoTnPc is equal to 1.16, and for CoTnPc/L (L = PYZ, 4,4'-bipy) 1.30. The ligand

(L) coordination to CoTnPc increases the electric vector perpendicular to the surface for all ligands and preparative methods under investigation; absorbance values are apparently increased for CoTnPc \rightarrow CoTnPc.L; in counterpart, the dichroic ratio is higher for surface derivatized CoTnPc/L, suggesting additional system ordering with increase of the positional angle related to the crystal structure and spin state if compared to isolated solids. All CoTnPc/L spectra are red-shifted (Table 3), showing that π -backbonding plays a minor role in the solid state.

Table 2 presents Q-band- λ_{\max} values and absorbance/layer for CoTnPc and CoTnPc/L compounds, the latter prepared by surface derivatization method.

Table 2		
Compd.	Q-band- λ_{\max}	Absorbance/layer
CoTnPc	686	0.012
CoTnPc/CN	694	0.020
CoTnPc/PYZ	698	0.030
CoTnPc/4-CN-PY	690	0.030
CoTnPc/4,4'-bipy	690	0.020

Fig. 5. Time dependence of slide immersion in concentrated ligand (L) solution Electronic absorption spectra of CoTnPc (1) LB deposited CoTnPc onto hydrophobic glass-slide, 20 layers, 10 cycles of Z type transfer; Q-band $\lambda_{\max} = 686$ nm, absorb 0.22, abs/layer 0.011, (2) immersion of (1) in aqueous NaCN-6 M, 90° , during 4 min, Q-band $\lambda_{\max} = 692$ nm, absorb 0.257, abs/layer 0.0128, (3) immersion of (1) in aqueous NaCN-6 M, 90° , during 12 min, Q-band $\lambda_{\max} = 696$ nm, abs 0.27, abs/layer 0.0135

By inspection of experimental data obtained by UV-visible measurements, Fig. 4(a) (upper reduced inset) shows absorption spectra for 8 layers of CoTnPc deposited by LB techniques onto hydrophobic glass slide, with absorbance per layer : 0.012. Fig. 4(b) presents the spectra of Co^{II} TnPc(-2) after removal (by washing) with DMSO; the Q-band is located at 676 nm, which shows that the compound presents stability. The weak band around 612 nm is typical of unaggregated species and due to vibrational modes. The solid state spectra (Fig. 4(a)) with broadening and shift to 686 nm, is attributed to solid state coupling or Davydov¹⁶ effects and generation of band structure due to intermolecular aggregation. The absorption spectra of both solid and liquid state of Pc species can provide a sensitive probe for the presence or absence of coupling between two (or more) Pc units. For the systems under investigation, CoTnPc presents a good correlation between solution species and solid films, attributed to a parallel arrangement of the Pc rings in the solid state. A solution at room temperature contains a selection of species from strongly coupled to uncoupled^{13a}; these effects may be enhanced in the solid state, once bidimensional processes present large preconcentration effects. By comparing Fig. 5(a) of CoTnPc.CN (hydrophilic deposition) to Fig. 4(a) (upper inset) CoTnPc (hydrophobic surfaces), it is found that both spectra are very similar. It is known that monomers and polymers present the same absorption spectra^{6a}, both systems CoTnPc and CoTnPc/L present a parallel arrangement for the Pc ring, with no lattice distortions due to L axial ligation.

Comparison of electronic spectra of LB deposited from toluene spreading solution CoTnPc.CN.5H₂O (1mM) with direct CN surface (Co) coordination, induced thermally in aqueous medium, reveals that the spectral differences are attributed to electronic and vibrational modes, strongly coupled due to inclusion of water molecules producing changes in lattice vibrational characteristics⁸. The displacive transition may be the result of vibrational instabilities, induced by changes on the molecular geometry. The band located at 620 nm (CoTnPcLB deposited onto hydrophilic glass slide) gets some intensity, which indicates that coupling is occurring to some extent¹³. The conversion of CoTnPc to CoTnPc/L on the surface is very abrupt; after 10–12 min time have elapsed (see Fig. 5) all reaction sites are occupied for CoTnPc/CN; in counterpart in the liquid phase absence of surface effects makes those processes extremely slow.

Conclusions : The results reveal the following : (i) CoTnPc/L prepared in solution (as powder) present electronic and crystal characteristics which distinguish it from the parent compound prepared on a bidimensional surface, in the presence of water. In the liquid state there are low cooperativity effects: total cooperativity is achieved in perfect crystals and non-cooperativity in gases or perfect solutions; cooperativity effects, and statistical considerations (small overlap of orbitals gives a high transitions probability), as thermal collisions and exchange partners turns the L-coordination to CoTnPc extremely slow in liquid medium; (ii) the surface coordination of L presents high kinetic rates due to the surface cooperativity effects—cooperative Jahn-Teller coupling between Co mediated by L bridges, and intramolecular distortions by considering the intermolecular coupling between distortions. Electron wave functions are lattice-constrained; solid-state transfer is essentially directional and open to control; energy associated with electron movement within the solvent is very small; (iii) CoTnPc/L compounds can be prepared with different spin states depending on reaction conditions; bidentate ligands (medium field) such as PYZ and 4,4'-bipy can form intermediate configurations between HS and LS. The transition temperature corresponds to a first order phase change with structure modification in the solid lattice. Such changes can be brought about by introduction of cooperative (lattice) modes which may be based upon rotational movements locally or vibrations, the latter called mode-softening transitions^{17a,17b}. The spin transition corresponds to an intraionic ($t_{2g} \rightarrow e_g$) electron transfer accompanied by the spin flip of the transferred electrons. For CoTnPc surface derivatized systems, the spin transition is thermally driven, and the fraction of HS residue depends on the method of preparation of the compound¹⁹ and ligand characteristics.

The variations in intermolecular contacts are driven by thermal contraction of lattice parameters over the temperature range and the strengthening of metal-ligand bonds (ΔR) upon spin transition.

Experimental

2,9,16,23-Tetra(neopentoxo)phthalocyaninatocobalt (CoTnPc) was prepared by literature methods^{2b,c}. CoTnPc/L compounds were prepared by 48 h reflux in the presence of a ten-fold excess of purified pyridine (PY) and the same procedure with ethanol as liquid medium for cyanide (CN), pyrazine (PYZ), 4,4'-bipyridyl (4,4'-bipy) and 4-cyanopyridine (4-CN-PY). On allowing the refluxed solutions to stand at room temperature for at least 72 h, the solvent was partially removed and the cobalt complexes crystallized from water. Elemental analysis conclusively proved that CoTnPc/L, contained 1 or 0.5 L unit.

LB experiments employed 1 mM toluene solutions of CoTnPc and CoTnPc/L as isolated solids. LB deposition of CoTnPc onto hydrophobic surfaces was clearly Z-type transfer, while CoTnPc/L deposition onto hydrophilic surfaces presented Y-type transfer.

Surface derivatized CoTnPc/L compounds were prepared by immersion of LB deposited CoTnPc layers onto hydrophobic surfaces in concentrated ligand (L) solutions (3–6 M) at 80–90°. Immersion or dipping time varied from 3 to 12 min.

Electronic spectra were recorded with a Hitachi-Perkin-Elmer microporocessor 340 and/or a Cary-2400 spectrometer. IR spectra (KBr) were determined for CoTnPc and CoTnPc/L and recorded with a FT-IR Nicolet equipment-Nicolet 20 SX-Instrument. ¹H NMR spectra (DMSO-*d*₆) were obtained on a Varian EM360 instrument.

A homemade Langmuir-Blodgett trough, designed according to Van Ryswyk *et al.*⁴ was used in the measurements of the surface pressure-area (π -A) isotherm of the monolayers at the air/water interface with an AppleII+ microcomputer controlled LB system using a local program. The water subphase was double-distilled over KMnO₄ and passed through a Barnstead organic removal cartridge and two Barnstead mixed-resin ultrapure cartridges. The monolayer was spread from a solution of CoTnPc or CoTnPc/L – 1.0×10^{-3} M in toluene or CH₂Cl₂ at 15°. The built-up LB films of the Pc complexes were deposited by transfer of the monolayers using the horizontal lifting method onto quartz slides (7.5 × 3.0 × 0.1 cm) which had been rendered hydrophobic by pretreatment with 5% (vol) dichlorodimethylsilane in CCl₄ at a surface pressure of 16 mN m⁻¹ (measurement based on Wilhelmy's principle), and compressed at a speed of 1.5 Å²/mol/min, with a dipping rate of 5 mm min⁻¹ in an X-type transfer for CoTnPc. The hydrophilic surfaces obtained after sonication in a 1 M NaOH solution were designed for the deposition of CoTnPc/L [L = cyanide (CN), pyridine (PY), 4-

cyanopyridine (4-CN-PY), pyrazine (PYZ), 4,4'-bipyridyl (4,4'-bipy)] in an Y-type transfer.

References

- (a) F. Cariati, D. Galizzioli, F. Morazzoni and C. Busetto, *J. Chem. Soc., Dalton Trans.*, 1975, 556; (b) F. Cariati, F. Morazzoni and M. Zocchi, *J. Chem. Soc., Dalton Trans.*, 1978, 1018; N. Fahmy, A. Leverenz and M. Hanack, *Synth. Met.*, 1991, 2615; (c) H. Ogoshi, N. Masai, Z. Yoshida, J. Takemoto and K. Nakamoto, *Bull. Chem. Soc. Jpn.*, 1971, 44, 49; (d) D. Wöhrle, 'Phthalocyanines in Polymer Phases' in "Phthalocyanines: Properties and Applications", eds. C. C. Leznoff and A. B. P. Lever, VCH Publishers, 1989.
- (a) J. Metz, O. Schneider and M. Hanack, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1984, 23, 1065; (b) C. C. Leznoff, S. M. Marcuccio, S. Greenberg, A. B. P. Lever and K. B. Tomer, *Can. J. Chem.*, 1985, 63, 623; (c) C. C. Leznoff, S. Greenberg, S. M. Marcuccio, P. C. Minor, P. Seymour and A. B. P. Lever, *Inorg. Chim. Acta*, 1985, 89, L35; (d) M. R. Hempsted, A. B. P. Lever and C. C. Leznoff, *Can. J. Chem.*, 1987, 65, 2677.
- (a) M. Hanack, S. Degar, and A. Lange, *Coord. Chem. Rev.*, 1988, 83, 115; (b) M. Hanack and M. Lang, *Adv. Mater.*, 1994, 6, 819.
- H. Van Ryswyk, J. M. Eisenhart and N. Blom, *Rev. Sci. Instrum.*, 1985, 56, 2339.
- (a) B. Stymne, F. X. Sauvage and G. Wettermark, *Spectrochim. Acta, Part A*, 1980, 36, 397; (b) 1979, 35, 1195.
- (a) J. Metz, O. Schneider and M. Hanack, *Spectrochim. Acta, Part A*, 1982, 38, 1265; (b) J. Metz and M. Hanack, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1983, 105, 828; (c) M. Burghard, M. Schmelzer, S. Roth, P. Haisch and M. Hanack, *Langmuir J.*, 1994, 10, 4265.
- P. C. Minor, M. Gouterman and A. B. P. Lever, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1985, 24, 1894.
- C. R. Johnson, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1991, 30, 2120.
- (a) N. Kobayashi, H. Lam, W. A. Nevin, P. Janda, C. C. Leznoff, T. Koyama, A. Monden and H. Shirai, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1994, 116, 879; (b) J. H. Kim, T. M. Cottom, R. A. Uphaus and C. C. Leznoff, *Thin Solid Films*, 1988, 159, 141; (c) Y. Liu, K. Shigehara and A. Yamada, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1991, 113, 440.
- A. Ruauadel-Teixier, *Mol. Cryst. Liq. Cryst.*, 1993, 43, 235.
- W. R. Barger, A. W. Snow, H. Wohltjen and N. Jarvis, *Thin Solid Films*, 1985, 133, 197.
- (a) Y. Fu and A. B. P. Lever, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1991, 95, 6979; (b) B. L. Wheeler, G. Nagasubramanian, A. J. Bard, L. A. Schechtman, D. R. Dinny and M. E. Kenney, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1984, 106, 7404; (c) N. Kobayashi and A. B. P. Lever, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1987, 109, 7433.
- (a) E. S. Dodsworth, A. B. P. Lever, P. Seymour and C. C. Leznoff, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1985, 89, 5689; (b) W. A. Newin, M. R. Hempstead, W. Liu, C. C. Leznoff and A. B. P. Lever, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1987, 26, 570.
- E. L. Ivchenko and G. Pikus, "Superlattices and Other Heterostructures", Springer-Verlag, Berlin, 1995.
- I. C. Khoo, "Physical Properties and Nonlinear Optical Phenomena", Wiley, New York, 1995.
- R. J. Madix, "Surface Reactions", Springer-Verlag, Berlin, 1994.
- (a) P. Gütlisch and A. Hauser, *Coord. Chem. Rev.*, 1990, 97, 247; (b) E. König, *Prog. Inorg. Chem.*, 1987, 35, 527; (c) E. König, G. Ritter and S. K. Kulshreshtha, *Chem. Rev.*, 1995, 85, 219.
- O. Kahn, J. Kröber and C. Jay, *Adv. Materials*, 1992, 4, 718.
- B. Gallois, J. A. Real, C. Hauw and J. Zarembowitch, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1990, 29, 1152.
- P. Thuery, J. Zarembowitch, A. Michalowicz and O. Kahn, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1987, 26, 851.